

THE ROLE OF STUDYING HISTORICAL MILITARY HEROES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MILITARY-PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *The article describes the development of military-professional competence, the studying of the lives of military heroes, the analysis of their actions and the further increase of military patriotism. The didactic possibilities of military history in the development of military-professional competence are analyzed.*

Keywords: *military-professional competence, patriotism, defense, ancient, military heritage, army, protection, professional, loyal.*

The study of military history occupies a special place in the development of military-professional competence. It is known that the science of military history is rich in many real examples of the military field. Each of these examples represents unique patriotic actions. It allows the student to learn about his country, people, the past lives of his ancestors, which is necessary for the education of patriotism in young people, to be able to correctly analyze and draw appropriate conclusions.

In fact, talking about the Motherland, the feeling of patriotism, and love for the Motherland was not common among our people. Our ancestors have proven their love and loyalty to their country and people in practice. The activities of our ancestors Shiroq and Spitamen, Jaloliddin Manguberdi and Amir Temur are a historical example. Bobur Ganiev, Ruslan Narziev, Kahramon Madolimov, Asilbek Mirzaev, Ulugbek Barnoev, who sacrificed their lives for the defense of the Motherland during the events in Surkhandarya and Tashkent regions, remained loyal to their people, the President and their military oath until their last breath.

One of the most important conditions for the protection of the independence and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the training of highly professional, loyal, selfless and courageous military personnel who are devoted to military and patriotic duty. According to historical sources, our ancestors were always distinguished by their courage, courage and dedication to the defense of the Motherland, and their military skills and courage were recognized by many nations. Our ancestors made a worthy contribution to the development of world military art. The names and exploits of brave, patriotic, courageous, great generals like Amir Temur and Muqanna are known and famous. Herodotus' work “History” vividly describes the valiant struggle of the Massagetae under the leadership of Tomaris against the Persian army. According to the personal secretary of Jaloliddin Manguberdi, who accompanied him in his military campaigns, the historian Nasavi wrote in his work “Siirat al-Sultan Jaloliddin Manguberdi”, “Jaloliddin was extremely determined, extremely strong-willed, a commander who did not lose himself in difficult situations and in the trials of fate”[1].

It is one of the most important tasks of today to make our students proud of the ancient history and culture of our country, our national heroes who selflessly fought for the independence and development of our beloved Motherland, and to always be worthy of them.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Sh.M. Mirziyoev, “It is important to deeply study the ancient history of our nation, the heritage of our great ancestors and their contribution to the development of military art in the implementation of measures aimed at further strengthening military-patriotic and moral education of military personnel. is important” [2]. Therefore, the history and culture of our ancestors, their heroism, and the spiritual heritage of our people will be a shining example in the development of the military-professional competence of the primary training teacher until the future recruitment in higher educational institutions.

As a talented and experienced military leader, Amir Temur left a deep mark on the development of military work and tactics in our homeland, he made a worthy contribution to the development of military science not only in Central Asia, but also in the world, to the formation of new methods and tactics. Amir Temur was the first in the history of world military art to introduce the order of deploying the army in seven arms on the battlefield. Hilda Hookham, a contemporary Anglian researcher of entrepreneurial personality, has shown the truth for the first time in Western psychology. “In the country where Timur was born,” writes the scientist, “universal works were created in philosophy, medicine, history, literature and other fields.” These works later gave impetus to the European renaissance” [3] We can conclude from this that the fifteenth century can be called the period of Timurid Renaissance. Amir Temur compared the state's division into twelve categories to the twelve months of the state, and thinking about the fifth category of these twelve categories, he said: “Whose intellect and courage I put on the test scales and found to be superior to others, I would take him under my tutelage and raise him to the rank of emirates...” [4]

Professor A.H.Daniy had been studying the history of the Timurids for a long time, and in his book “Timur Legacy” written in English, he notes such thoughts: Temur met scientists and creative people there, had lively conversations with them and created conditions for them...” [5] In recent years, large-scale work has been carried out to consistently reform and develop the national army, strengthen the defense capabilities of our country, and train military personnel. The adoption of the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism, the strengthening of cooperation with local state authorities to ensure the unity of the army and the people, makes it possible to fill the ranks of our national army with young people who have a strong will and an active civil position.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 30, 2017 “On improving the effectiveness of state policy regarding youth” and the Cabinet of Ministers' decision No. 140 dated February 23, 2018 “On educating youth in the spirit of military patriotism” protect the rights, freedoms and legal interests of young people, it is emphasized the importance of education in the spirit of respect for national and universal values, loyalty to the ideas of independence in the mind and heart, awareness of national identity, love for the Motherland and attachment to its destiny, determination and development of self-sacrifice, protection from various ideological threats [6]. Including, to educate young people about their constitutional duties in the defense of the Motherland, to create a foundation for them to fulfill their honorable duty of protecting their country from any armed aggression, to gain their faith and interest in the military

profession, as well as to protect themselves and others in emergency situations, and to preserve the spiritual and material resources of our country. training of selfless and patriotic members of our society who can take reasonable initiative on the way is seen as an important task.

Regarding the history, we should direct our intellectual potential to the most noble and priority goals, such as the well-being of our people, the peace of our country and the purity of our sky, the building of a free and prosperous Motherland, and a free civil society, as a means of fully demonstrating our intelligence and energy.

Studying the lives and activities of world-famous scholars and generals who lived and worked in our country, their role and importance in the development of human civilization is one of the most important issues for patriotic education.

The names of our brave ancestors who sacrificed their lives for the Motherland in ancient history will never be forgotten. One of our great compatriots, Najmuddin Kubro, who has a life as an example to the youth of today, chose to be a victim in the struggle for the freedom of the Motherland by the mercy of a tyrant like Genghis Khan, and with his exemplary selflessness, he showed that patriotism does not choose age, a person with strong love for his country even at the age of 76. proved that he can find strength in himself to fight against the enemy, which is the highest manifestation of loyalty to the Motherland and love for the people.

Jaloliddin Manguberdi was brave and patriotic son of our people, a scholar of military art, attacked the Mongolian army of thousands in order to liberate the country. Although he did not completely defeat the enemy, he caused chaos in their ranks. His courage, strong will, and boundless love for his country and people impressed even a general like Genghis Khan. It was a high display of military skill to destroy the army and thereby arouse feelings of envy and jealousy. In addition, Jaloliddin Manguberdi's national pride was strong and he did not want to see his livers in slavery in the hands of the enemy.

Military-patriotic education and training in general secondary and secondary special, vocational educational institutions is carried out in the training of pre-call up military education and other subjects.

Based on the analyzes of the “Military History” science program, we witnessed the absence of topics and didactic units related to the development and content of military-professional competence in primary teachers until the upcoming convocation, and the content of the topics covered in the science program was improved based on the military-professional competence approach. In particular:

- Military-professional training in the military campaigns of Amir Temur;
- Development of the military-professional competence of pre-call up military education based on Timur's rules;
- The role of the military art of our great generals in the development of the military-professional competence of the pre-call up military education;
- The development of military-professional competence of students of pre-call military education is part of the reforms carried out in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Effective formation of military-professional competence of future teachers in the study of national military heritage;
- The role of military-professional competence in the study of classic military strategy;

We can say that within the framework of the above recommended topics, as an example, Mulla Holbek bin Mulla Musa's “Alimqul Janganma” shows the presence of quick attack elements

in the process of providing defense as a unique aspect of the classic military strategy, or the “shiba” and “shundulomishi” methods of retreating are described, and these methods are used in the military structures of NATO member states. is widely used. It is appropriate to include topics about historical military strategies in the curriculum of “Military History” [7].

Sh. N. Durmenov's textbook “Military History” states that with the emergence of the army, an important component of combat activity is practical military history, which serves as a necessary and mandatory tool for the successful implementation of all-round combat actions of the military [8].

During our research, we can conclude on the subject of “Military History” that, until the upcoming draft, the primary training teacher will develop military thinking in the minds of students by conveying military historical events in educational institutions, give them military-pedagogical recommendations, and among them, correctly, we felt that it should be targeted. It is in this process that the urgency of developing the military-professional competence of the primary training teacher before the upcoming call-up is clearly demonstrated.

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